

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF WATCHING CARTOONS TO IMPROVE THE KNOWLEDGE OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE OF YOUNG CHILDREN

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Annotation: This article information about the influences of the cartoons in the process of teaching young learners to English language. The reactions of the learners to the audiovisual materials prepared by the teacher and the importance of choosing the relevant aids considering the desire and abilities of the learners to maintain the effective learning atmosphere.

Key words: children, cartoon, teaching, audiovisual materials.

INTRODUCTION

Effective learning requires the usage of divergent techniques in the sphere of foreign language. Teacher chooses the method according to the both availability of the materials and relevance to the topic. Existing a number of methods and techniques to conduct effective lesson and they depend on the level of the learners and the level of the difficulty of the task. There are teachers who find benefit from simple things whereas also those who make the easy things challenging. Young learners are considered as both super active and the laziest at the same time, sometimes it might seem that teaching children is the most difficult stage while there are also the moments when teacher enjoys by the atmosphere among children since they find interesting the simplest cartoon scenes interesting. Moreover, the role of cartoons in teaching English makes great contribution because they are colorful and attractive.

There are many positive sides of using AV – audiovisual media in class (Arsyad 2008) [1]. The first one is that AV aids to improve the activeness and interest of the learners which helps to develop strong basic blocks of the language. They get engaged in the lessons when they hear and see the motions and voice details in English. The cartoons which they used to watch in L1 start to appear in L2, learners' tension of the lesson is relieved and start to feel free to accept the information. According to Daryanto (2010) [2] there are some other functions of media use in teaching i.e. it: helps the teacher to transfer the knowledge to the learners; can save the teacher's energy; motivates learners to learn by seeing the pictures; make the learners focus more on the pictures and they try to understand what the actor says; and increases the amount of teaching and learning as the learners are getting input both from the teachers and the AV media.

There are a number of significant impacts on child when they start to be implemented the AV material in English language, not only they will learn new words, but also from the very beginning of learning they will get used to English accent and pronounce the words in the way as the real natives, they will be able to comprehend the conversations of native speaking, by watching their favorite cartoons. However, there are also the conditions when the teacher has to be very attentive while choosing the type of AV for the class that he/she is going to teach due to the fact that, if the learner start to feel challenges or there no familiar words in the context in these cases they neglect watching them with enthusiasm and get

simply distracted by other things such as talking to the partners or show disrespect to the teacher.

It is obvious that the AV media can support pupils to better remember the vocabulary items (Kittidachanupap 2012) [4]. When the learners see the various content-based presentations, especially those which children like in their daily life, evokes the interest to the lesson and influences on the creativity. Different colorful images and sounds develop the creativity which is important not only in the sphere of language, but also science, mathematics, arts as well. This study is also beneficial for the language teachers of kindergarten and primary education because the demand for the awareness of at least basic concepts of English is becoming essential and this can be understood by the fact that, teachers working in kindergarten also have to own a language certificate of B2 level.

The content of the lesson has impact on the children's acceptance of information, Kausar (2013) [3] in her findings described Pakistani learners. According to her Pakistani learners efficiently replace boring education atmosphere with wonderful and feasible education classroom. The classroom atmosphere depends on the teacher's competence and creativity, yet the learners show activeness when the lesson is not the same as usual, when the material are out from daily tasks, they attract attention. Children are hyper active learners and eager to investigate new things and ready to undergo experiences. If the topic is about the weather, introducing cartoons demonstrating constant change of weather and words might be unusual, as a result improvement in pronouncing words correctly start to be noticed. The cartoons are mostly dialogues, consisting of conversation between one or two people, this way children might improve the fluency of their speech since they love imitating the main character from their favorite cartoon. Common phrases from the contexts of natives from cartoons can be the newly constructed words for children because they may not know the actual meaning of the words such as "take care", "go ahead" however through the dialogue they will start to comprehend the meaning by guessing from the gestures and signals they make.

To conclude, the necessity of cartoons as a part of teachers' tool to create for children more interesting exercises is the key to success not only in conducting the lesson effectively, but also giving learners a chance to enjoy the lesson unconsciously together by expanding their knowledge. Somehow cartoons have the features of being education and interesting at the same time.

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